

1 **Molecular mechanisms underlying peanut butter allergy.**

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6 Our laboratory studies food and nutrition as it pertains to public health. Peanut harvesting was refined
7 through agricultural techniques and peanut based foodstuffs were introduced to provide readily available,
8 taste-accessible protein to children and adults in the community. Peanut butter allergies are now common
9 in schools and among children. We studied here the molecular basis of peanut butter allergy by measuring
10 total transcription by microarray in human myeloid dendritic cells following 24 hour in vitro exposure to
11 peanut protein. Exposure of human dendritic cells to peanut allergen resulted in activation of *Cd1a*, *Cd1b*
12 and *Cd1c* while silencing *Cd14*. We observed activation of a TNF superfamily receptor by peanut allergen,
13 *Tnfrsf21*. Cytokines induced by exposure to peanut protein included IL1RN and *IL1RAP*. Allergen
14 exposure resulted in induction of genes associated with cellular damage including *TIMP3*, *LPL* and
15 *PLAUR*. *TLR7*, *TLR8* and *TLR5* were each repressed by exposure peanut allergen. C-type lectins *Clec10a*
16 and *Clec4a* were silenced by in vitro peanut protein exposure, as was *Ms4a14*. *Fcgr2b* was silenced by in
17 vitro exposure to peanut allergen as was HLA-DQB1.

18 Citations

19 1. Anagnostou, A., Brough, H.A. and Abrams, E.M., 2026. Peanut allergy. *JAMA*, 335(17),
20 pp.1527-1528.

21 2. Sampson, H.A., 2002. Peanut allergy. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 346(17), pp.1294-1299.

22 3. Lack, G., Fox, D., Northstone, K. and Golding, J., 2003. Factors associated with the development
23 of peanut allergy in childhood. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 348(11), pp.977-985.

24 4. Du Toit, G., Roberts, G., Sayre, P.H., Bahnson, H.T., Radulovic, S., Santos, A.F., Brough, H.A.,
25 Phippard, D., Basting, M., Feeney, M. and Turcanu, V., 2015. Randomized trial of peanut consumption in
26 infants at risk for peanut allergy. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 372(9), pp.803-813.

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28 GSE13619

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